

THE METHODOLOGY OF ASSESSMENTS IN THE TEACHING- LEARNING PROCESS: CONTRIBUTION OF SCHÈME DE PIAGET IN DIDACTICS

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Abstract

The evaluation system in basic education has several flaws. The objective of this article is to observe how assessments are made in teaching and the possibility of using Schème de Piaget to improve didactics. A bibliographical research on the method of evaluation and methodologies used by the teachers was carried out. It was concluded that there are several ways to carry out evaluations, such as educational games, software and applications, or to follow the needs of each student.

Keywords: Evaluation. Teaching-learning. Scheme. Piaget.

Introduction

The theme to be addressed by this work will be how the teaching-learning process is interconnected with the assessment system. It cannot be denied that human beings have the need to evaluate everything around them. At all times, people evaluate and are evaluated in most activities carried out in daily life.

The school also follows this pattern. There is a need to assess the student and their learning according to the period of study of a given content covered. The school still has assessment systems considered obsolete, where what the student learned is not assessed, but what the teacher elaborated on that test.

Therefore, it is necessary to find out how this assessment is carried out and how this system can be adapted to current education. To carry out this work, a bibliographical research on the subject was carried out and the final text was elaborated.

Theoretical Reference

2.1. The Assessment System linked to the Teaching-Learning Process

The classes of the various subjects taught in basic education, including elementary school I, elementary school II and high school, have a standard model, governed by the school's rules. This model is based on the principle of dividing study periods during the academic year, usually in four quarters. These bimonths are subdivided into smaller parts to better accommodate the content to be delivered.

The bimonthly division and its subdivisions are based on the school's needs. These needs in turn are determined by the State Department of Education. This parameter determined by higher authorities makes the teacher stuck in the calendar established by the educational institution (SILVA and NAVARRO, 2012).

In this sense, the teacher has the role of managing what should happen at each time of the calendar divisions, and must also manage the content to be taught. This content is often longer than the amount of time you have available. In addition, it must also manage the division of the score of that bimester (PIRONEL and ONUCHIC, 2016). At this point, the way in which student assessments should be carried out enters.

Schools usually already establish the division of points and the evaluation model, which usually occupy 50% of the bimonthly score. In this model, the number of questions that must be from multiple schools and the essays is already defined.

In this context, where everything already has a preset, whether from the school or higher authorities, it means that the teacher cannot really make his assessment according to his needs. He has the function of teaching and evaluating according to this methodology. However, this evaluation system has major flaws.

According to Dos Santos Lemos (2013), "when there is contact with new information, in a teaching situation or not, the individual can learn or not learn the new meaning." Thus, when the student fails to reach the average for passing, he is considered by logic, failed and seen as someone who has not learned the content. The teacher, in turn, is seen as a professional who cannot adequately teach that topic. This assessment system only attests whether the student is able or not to proceed to the next stage of content and studies.

It is important that the teacher recognizes and assumes his role as a stimulator and mediator of the student's knowledge and knowledge, and the assessment methods. Silva and Navarro (2012) emphasize that it is up to the teacher to act as an intermediary between the learning contents and the constructive activity for assimilation.

The ideal assessment is one based on the experiences that the student takes to school. The knowledge brought by the student must be used during the teaching and learning process. This knowledge must be added to the scientific knowledge acquired in the student institution and based on that, the assessment should be established.

The assessment has to be carried out through the practice and knowledge of the students. The teacher must plan in this context and know how to evaluate the student according to their needs and difficulties, concerning that discipline or in an interdisciplinary process (SILVEIRA, 2019). The assessment must take place at all times, daily in all actions of the students.

Thus, a resource to be used are didactic games, which value contextualized, playful and practical teaching. According to Campos, Bortoloto and Felicio,

[...] the game gains a space as the ideal learning tool, as it proposes to stimulate the student's interest, develops different levels of personal and social experience, helps to build their new discoveries, develops and enriches their personality, and symbolizes a pedagogical instrument that takes the teacher to the condition of conductor, stimulator and evaluator of learning (CAMPOS, BORTOLOTO, FELÍCIO, 2003, p.48).

Given the strategy of using games as a teaching and learning method, they also present themselves as an excellent tool for evaluating the learning of Biology contents, which are seen as complex and difficult for students to assimilate.

The educational game is a means that encourages the construction of knowledge in a collective and collaborative way. This means of approach allows the student to dialogue with their own colleagues and with the teacher. During this interaction, doubts can be resolved and an assessment can be carried out.

The learning assessment strategy can occur through other means besides educational games, such as the use of technologies: computer, social networks, application software and other multimedia means.

Pironel and Onuchic (2016, p.8) suggest that the assessment process should be carried out “through Problem Solving, teaching, learning and assessment occur simultaneously and the assessment is carried out by both the teacher and the student”. The great advantage of this model is that, in addition to the student being evaluated, the teacher can check where failures may have occurred and redo the planning with classes that reduce the student's gap.

Assessment through problem solving allows the student to participate in the assessment process, together with the teacher. From this perspective, both can discuss and analyze which points can be improved and how the learned content will be used during the academic and personal career.

It is necessary to emphasize that the evaluation process must be constant, daily and with the participation of groups of students. The school, its management and coordination must assist in this methodology, offering instruments together with teachers to establish a differentiated system for evaluating students. Thus, rethinking the teaching format that is offered is a primordial task for the beginning of this stage.

This assessment model, which values the experience and ease of problem solving in the disciplines, provides the student with the construction of collective and collaborative knowledge, the development of critical sense, opinion formation, in addition to providing adequate training as a citizen. All efforts used to assess students adequately and fairly, will contribute to an education with improvements and quality.

2.2. The Schème de Piaget in the Teaching-Learning Process and in the Assessment System

In view of the assessment models proposed by the education system, the importance of Piaget's schème model for learning is highlighted. The teacher must act as a learning facilitator, proposing problems to students, without teaching them the solutions, in the sense of provoking learning and making challenges.

For the success of this type of learning, it is of fundamental importance for the teacher to conceive and understand the subject, as Piaget (1964), in its entirety, in the communion of development and learning as dependent processes, in order to create situations and learning environments, which “destabilize the student in order to lead him to a response that is essentially due to external stimuli, with the aim of improving learning”.

The notion of schème for learning leads to better conduction in the teaching and learning process, in the sense of knowing and establishing interactions between the teacher's good knowledge and the students' intellectual capacity, thus also providing a better model for evaluating the performance of students. students.

2.3. The Schème de Piaget applied in the teaching-learning process

Learning happens when it reaches different levels that Vergnaud (1997) describes in three phases: when the set of symbol representations are linked to socialize the concept; the second phase is the set of operational invariants or properties of the concept and finally, the third phase when there is a set of situations that make the concept meaningful.

In this way, the concept is something that improves as you learn more about it. When the individual acquires an apprenticeship, there is the interconnection of these concepts and forming the conceptual field. Knowing how the interpellation of concepts works, it is possible to analyze the schemes.

Given the existence of this element in the functioning of the Piagetian scheme, it allows making inferences about the knowledge underlying the organizations of individuals' actions. Therefore, it enables improvements in both teaching and learning, and also in this process as a whole.

When the schème is used as a form of analysis, it is possible to define a concept in light of the individual's situation or representation. Taking this line of analysis, it is possible to determine the learning obtained when comparing sets of invariants.

According to Rabardel (1995), contrary to the definition of common sense, the concept of instrument represents the combination of a scheme and an artifact. The latter refers to artifacts such as parts of a computational interface. The learning seen in this perspective is seen as a series of stages of concepts to be incorporated into the construction of the schema.

The element that makes up the instrument is the notion of schème, which does not exist innately in objects. With this aggregation of artifacts, it allows the analysis of instruments and subjects and their due adaptations. But Rabardel (1995) reports that this allows for an analysis of the conceptual development following adaptation to a new instrument.

Learning according to Piaget and Gréco (1959/1974) can follow two paths: understanding or simple discrimination, in which it is directed towards empirical knowledge. The important thing is not to learn, but how to learn, so that the subject can develop their

learning in structured knowledge. Piaget explains this as a “set of possible and/or virtual operations” that can be updated in the subject's conduct.

In this scenario, what happens beyond learning generates meaning and the possibility of middle-end coordination. It is worth adding that due to the imbalance that learning can cause, there is always the possibility of building knowledge about a given phenomenon, as mentioned by De Queiroz, Canal and Ronchi (2012).

Piaget and Gréco (1959/1974) also point out that what is learned are differentiations due to accommodation, “[...] source of new schemes due to the growing diversity of contents” (p.85), and that incorporations are not learned due to assimilation, “[...] the assimilating functioning with its demands for balance between assimilation and accommodation, source of the gradual coherence of the schemes and their organization [...]” (p.86).

For Piaget, learning leads the individual to form empirical knowledge without understanding. With that, it can bring durable and generalizable structures, partially and with limited mobility. It is noteworthy that it can only be said as meaningful learning, when it intervenes in the knowledge process, through dialectics, in which learning and knowledge become complementary and not opposite.

Learning takes place in an ascending movement of knowledge composition processes that, through balancing, seek the descending movement of knowledge justification, finally, reaching the understanding of action, meaning it beyond success.

Currently, in schools, students may be endowed with more advanced cognitive abilities, which may be connected to the internet, social networks, etc, and others with greater learning difficulties. This fact has made it necessary for educators to take this new student into account when developing learning strategies for the contents of their classes. The challenge for a teacher today is to create educational strategies that are really meaningful to students, in order to attract their attention to their studies.

In this way, the school must become a place of cooperation, open discussion, dialogue between disciplines and specialties, circulation of people and knowledge, in which both autonomy and the capacity for exchange between teachers and students (co-authorships). It is worth remembering that this does not mean that the teacher will be "replaced", or even stripped of his role, but that his power of action will be increased, opening up new spaces for learning and rescuing the role of learners in construction and co-authorship.

Learning must constantly rebuild itself, as its very essence is in its own transformation, of continuous construction. The teacher must be aware of the changes, reconstructions and reorganizations of ideas that occur from the negotiation of objectives, the ways to reach them and the reformulations in their own inter-individual relationships.

Discussions

The teaching and learning process that leads to the understanding of the subject (both teacher and student) as an epistemic subject; a being who knows and builds knowledge.

Piaget shows that not every response given as a function of a given stimulus constitutes learning, so that only in the face of the diachronic record can one speak of learning, as a succession of movements and actions takes place there.

It emphasizes the importance of decentralizing the figure of the teacher in student learning. The teacher continues with their functions to teach and the student to learn, but it is important that the teacher does not deliver ready-made answers to the student, but rather that he seeks the proper answers in his daily life.

The teacher, in this way, is a mediating agent of learning. For this, it is essential that he knows the potential and difficulties of each student. Thus, he has the possibility of performing a differentiated work in the classroom with the same content. Although in the same classroom the topic addressed is the same, it is necessary that adaptations are punctual, in order to provide the student with imitations, knowledge and learning of law for academic and citizen education.

Conclusions

Educational institutions present teaching and learning models that are considered to be out of date with the current scenario in which we live. Education is currently based on the use of technologies and instruments that facilitate learning.

It can also be said that in addition to the teaching-learning process itself being obsolete, the assessment system also has several flaws. Most of the time, evaluations are carried out through tests, with the number of multiple choice questions and essays already pre-established by the school.

When the school stipulates the assessment format, it disregards the teacher's methodology in relation to their subject. Each teacher could use different methodological resources to carry out student assessment. This scenario must be modified and updated in face of current Education.

There are several ways that assessments can be carried out, whether through educational games, software and applications or even following the needs of each student.

A model of great relevance cited is through problem solving. In this system, the students together build knowledge collectively and collaboratively, with interaction among their own colleagues and with the teacher. In this way, the teacher has the ability to know at which points the students' learning was satisfactory and where there was a gap.

Finally, the importance of the teacher's planning according to the difficulties and needs of each student is highlighted. It is also worth emphasizing the great responsibility of the teacher in knowing how to select teaching materials to be used in their classes, making the teaching-learning process occur in a dynamic and integral way, in addition to carrying out a fair evaluation system according to demand. established by current Education.

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